

DEVELOPMENT OF RECREATION AND TOURIST CLUSTER OF ZONES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article discusses the formation of a tourism cluster on the basis of sustainable development for recreational areas of the territories of Uzbekistan. It also systematizes data on recreational areas in order to develop tourist routes and the spatial organization of natural areas of Uzbekistan in order to implement the state program "the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on tourism" №549 and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan - "On measures to create a tourist and recreational zone - Zomin and an international all-season resort".

Key words: recreational areas, cluster, sustainable development, tourist routes, potential of recreational areas.

Introduction

Recreational resources are an important part of the natural potential of the region. In addition, their role in the formation and development of modern tourism in the region is constantly increasing, especially from an ecological and geographical point of view.

Recreational zones of Uzbekistan lead you through deserted steppes, winding mountain roads, through deserts and noisy rivers to centuries-old cities. Going to Uzbekistan, you dedicate your time to more ancient and popular routes like Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. The ethnographic historical and cultural role of ancient architecture and urban planning is as important as the development of the recreational segment for tourism in such areas as tourist camps, rest houses and sanatoriums. In addition, it is necessary to take into account recreational tourism - as a type of recreation through the movement of people in their free time for the purpose of relaxation, necessary to restore physical, intellectual, mental strength and needs.

Uzbekistan Sunny country with sharply continental climate. The nature here is arid, but with fertile soil, there is little precipitation. In the region, the city of Tashkent is the most well-studied in the entire Central Asian land.

The state has no access to the sea and compensates for this with a large number of natural and artificial reservoirs and large lakes, rivers, covering the whole of Central Asia. Tourist opportunities in the region are very diverse and rich.

These include:

- Ugam-Chatkal Natural National Park
- Gissar Mountain Arch Reserve.
- Kyzylkum tugai-sand reserve.
- The region of "environmental catastrophe" near the Aral Sea.
- Surkhan mountain and forest reserve.
- Zaravshansky long-tugai reserve.
- Kitab National Geological Park.
- Nurata mountains and Aydarkul lake in Jizzakh region and many other natural wonders.

Two hours on the road from the city of Tashkent, you find yourself surrounded by picturesque mountains. Charvak mountain reservoir, Beldersay resort area, and Amirsoy ski resort, in the Tashkent region. People come here to breathe clean mountain air, go skiing, take a break from the bustle of the city, sunbathe in the hot season, go hiking. Walk on a chairlift, 3 km long, which is served by 26 cabins, climbing to a height of 2300 meters to Mount Kumbel. Descent by chairlift and transfer to the Chimgan tract (15 minutes from the Beldersay resort

area).

II. Introduction to terms

2.1 Research area

In order to understand what a cluster of recreational and tourist areas is, it is necessary to analyze each word separately: what does a cluster mean; what are the tourist areas and the potential of recreational areas in Uzbekistan.

2.2 Tourism sector for sustainable development.

Today, tourism, as a sector of the world economy, occupies the main place in terms of the turnover of services, the second - in terms of foreign exchange earnings, after oil refining. According to the World Tourism Organization, 8 percent of the world's employed population is owned by tourists. In addition, 7% of investment in the manufacturing and non-manufacturing sectors is tourism and 11% of total consumer spending. The tourist and recreational sphere is not only one of the largest and highly profitable, but also the most dynamically developing. For three decades in many countries of the world, tourism has turned from a relatively isolated service sector into a powerful spatially localized or dispersed inter-industry complex with pronounced multiplier effects of economic development.

As it is written in the “law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on tourism” № 549:

Forms of tourism are international and domestic tourism. International tourism includes:

- inbound tourism - travel within the Republic of Uzbekistan of persons who do not

permanently reside in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- outbound tourism - travel of persons permanently residing in the Republic of Uzbekistan to another country.

- Domestic tourism includes travel within the Republic of Uzbekistan of persons permanently residing in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Tourism, based on the specifics of the organized tour, themes, duration, modes of transportation and other characteristics of the tour, can be divided into cultural and historical, pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, business, social, sports, medical, youth, agro-tourism and other types tourism.

In order to comprehensively develop tourism and maintain tourism resources in good condition, increase the tourism potential of the relevant territory, as well as stimulate the attraction of investments in their development, the following types of tourist zones can be created:

- free tourist zone;
- small tourist zone;
- special tourist zone.

There are all 3 types of tourist areas in Uzbekistan. The first tourist zone is being created in the country, with the status of a free economic zone – Charvak.

2.3 Sustainability

Sustainable development is a harmonious and balanced development. It is a process of change in which the exploitation of natural resources, the direction of investment, the orientation of scientific and technological development, the development of the individual and institutional change is aligned with each other and strengthen the current and future capacity to meet human needs and aspirations. In many ways, it is about ensuring the quality of life of people.

The term sustainable development began to gain currency in the late 1980s, after its emergence in our common future, also known as the Brundtland Report. This report - the result of a commission convened by the United Nations to propose a "global agenda for change" in the concept and practice of development - noted the importance of urgently reflecting on our ways of life and governance.

In connection with the potential of natural resources and the possibility of organizing tourist zones for sustainable development, the systematic distribution and competent use of earth resources, it is proposed to form a cluster for the development of recreational and tourist zones on suitable lands in the country.

In line with the priorities outlined in the Global Guidelines for Tourism Resurgence, this framework is designed to help develop and implement recovery plans that contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the implementation of the Paris Agreement.

In order to resume tourism in accordance with the principle of "Building back better", it is necessary to ensure "Responsible Recovery".

2.3 Tourism cluster

A tourist cluster in urban planning is a set of heterogeneous (both in terms of ownership and functions) recreational facilities that provide comprehensive tourist and other related services necessary to meet the needs of tourists and sightseers.

Tourism clusters form, promote and implement a tourism product in order to provide comprehensive tourism services, increase competitiveness and quality of tourism activities.

In turn, the cluster approach is the basis for creating new forms of knowledge pooling, stimulating the emergence of new scientific and technical areas and their commercial applications, as well as indirectly supporting education, university science and venture business.

UNWTO Tourism Concepts Cluster
Communication of the tourism cluster on the basis of sustainable development with other clusters.

3.2 Stages of territorial formation of a recreational and tourist area

A feature of recreational zoning is that it affects both natural and socio-economic objects and phenomena. Consequently, this is an integral process that links the natural prerequisites with the social and economic needs of the development of the territory. Despite the important role of the natural component, it is the needs of socio-cultural development that determine the formation of recreational areas.

4. Conclusion

The final part of the article contains recommendations for the conservation and sustainable development, as well as the use of recreational areas in Uzbekistan. When choosing a territory, the ecological, geographical and economic state of the territory, the convenience of the camp site's reach is taken into account; how effectively the goal of tourism clusters will be achieved on the basis of sustainable development and how effectively it is connected with other clusters for the convenience of people, for the conservation of natural resources, taking into account the climatic conditions of the territory. This article is just a drop in the ocean, as the first step in developing principles for the development and organization of tourist areas with a systematic distribution and competent use of earth resources.

5. Literature

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